

Proving Logic in Graphs using Path Composition

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ABSTRACT

We give the new algorithm for proving facts in logical directed graph using dynamic programming approach.

Keywords: boolean, logic, proof, graphs, dynamic programming.

INTRODUCTION

The boolean logic is a way of expressing the boolean expressions [1, 2, 3], recently the new methodology was proposed [4].

The satisfiability problem is another concept [5] for which we give the weighted MAX-SAT algorithm based upon the estimation of sets.

ALGORITHM

We simply go through the graph by constructing strongly connected components and searching the new rule once all the incoming facts are satisfied.

As per our latest research the regular grammars and languages defined by regular expressions can be used as well in order to represent the logical processes within general and stochastic model.

WEIGHTED MAX-SAT

It can be noted that weight of any variable can be approximated and made tractable within its counted rate in satisfied conditions in boolean logical formula, based upon this we can give the weights with maximum cost and apply a greedy algorithm for searching the correct assignment of boolean variables in each of the clauses.

CONCLUSION

We have given a concise definition of what is to be proved using logical rules or what is to be satisfied in the MAX-SAT problem, both cases illustrate the classical example of the machine approach in giving the solution to the stated problems.

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